

Start on Sustainability Starter Kit

INTRODUCTION

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ABOUT OUR PROJECT

By implementing Start on Sustainability, we aim **to equip micro-enterprises** with the necessary **tools and resources** to take meaningful action towards sustainability, thereby contributing to a more sustainable and resilient EU economy.

SOS Starter Kit Table of Contents

UNIT NAME

Introduction to the SOS Starter Kit

Unit 1- Sustainable Business Operations

Unit 2- Sustainable Thinking

Unit 3- Engaging Staff

Unit 4- Serving Green Consumers

Unit 5- Community Partnerships

Unit 6- Assessment and Planning

UNIT NAME

Unit 7- Supply Chain Transparency

Unit 8- Benchmark Practices

Unit 9- Digital Tools

Unit 10- Pitfalls in Sustainable Businesses

Summary to the SOS Starter Kit

Key Terms and Definitions

References

INTRODUCTION TO THE SOS STARTER KIT

01

OVERVIEW OF THE TOPIC

02

OBJECTIVES

03

REFERENCES

OVERVIEW

- The concept of sustainable development was introduced in 1987 by the Brundtland Commission in their document "Our Common Future."
- Sustainable development approach seeks to fulfil the needs of current generations without jeopardising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs.
- It recognizes that economic growth is necessary to provide essentials like clean water and food, while also acknowledging the challenge of environmental damage often associated with economic progress.

ORIGIN

- The term "sustainability" was first used in the 1700s, originating from the German term "nachhaltigkeit," which translates to "sustained yield" in English.
- The term was coined to describe the practice of harvesting enough trees to ensure forests can naturally regenerate for the long term.
- The concept further broadened moving beyond forestry but still mainly confined to research and science.

- In 1972 The Ecologist published the Blueprint for Survival, a series of scientific papers advocating for better resource management and changes in consumer behaviours in western societies.
- A global think-tank released the report Limits to Growth, providing a definition for sustainability. The term was defined as the ability to avoid sudden collapses and meet the basic needs of all people.

EVOLUTION

- In 1972, the United Nations hosted a world conference on the human environment in Stockholm, where the term sustainable development was introduced.
- Throughout the 1980s, the concept of sustainability gained increasing prominence.

DEFINITION

- Sustainability and sustainable development are related concepts that focus on the environment, society, and economy over time.
- However, they have distinct meanings and should not be used interchangeably.

DEFINITION

Sustainable development is defined as meeting present needs without compromising future generations' ability to meet their own needs. It involves integrating environmental health, social equity, and economic vitality to create thriving, healthy, diverse, and resilient communities.

Sustainability recognizes the interconnectedness of these issues and requires a systems approach and acknowledgement of complexity. It supports ecological, human, and economic health and vitality, assuming finite resources should be used conservatively and wisely. In essence, sustainability is about our children and grandchildren, and the world we will leave them.

DEFINITION

Sustainability involves actions that protect the environment while also meeting social, cultural, and economic needs. Its goal is to conserve the natural world and shift away from our current resource-heavy lifestyle. This means living within the limits of available resources to ensure the well-being of all living creatures in the future.

On the other hand, sustainable development involves creating growth and progress by incorporating physical, economic, environmental, and social aspects to enhance quality of life without depleting environmental resources. It aims to ensure that resources are used without being exhausted.

**There is a path to sustainability.
It is a path that could lead to a better
future for all life on Earth**

David Attenborough

SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS

The United Nations introduced the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in 2015, comprising 17 global goals and 169 targets aimed at fostering a more sustainable planet and the quality of human life around the world by the year 2030.

SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS

- The objective is to "Leave no one behind," with a focus on reaching those furthest behind first and improve their quality of life.
- SDGs were formulated to address the shortcomings of the Millenium Development Goals (MDGs).

SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS

- SDGs focus on the three dimensions of sustainability: Social, Economic, and Environmental.
- These dimensions are interconnected, with progress in one area influencing others, and they must be addressed simultaneously.

SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS

- Sustainable Development seeks to strike a balance between meeting current needs without compromising the needs of future generations.
- It recognizes the importance of respecting nature while advancing human development across various aspects of the world.

SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS

- It aims to efficiently utilise resources while also meticulously planning the accomplishment of immediate as well as long-term goals for human beings, the future generations and the planet as well.
- In the present time, the need for Sustainable Development is not only for the survival of mankind but also for its future protection.

UNITED NATIONS

- The United Nations (UN) emphasises the importance of businesses in achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).
- Businesses can help by avoiding problems that governments have to address, such as pollution, poverty, and supporting war and conflict.
- They can also collaborate with others through sustainable operations, responsible investment, and innovation.

UNITED NATIONS

- The SDGs present both duties and opportunities for businesses.
- Successful implementation of the SDGs will strengthen the environment for doing business and building markets.
- However, even responsible companies face challenges such as instability in communities, difficulty in finding skilled labour, and unprecedented natural disasters due to climate change.

UNITED NATIONS

- The UN and others recognise that profit will continue to be a main motive for many companies, and some may need to be monitored.
- The UN acknowledges that working within the existing business environment could lead to better commitment.

Sustainable Development aims to efficiently utilise resources and plan for immediate and long-term goals for human survival, the planet, and future generations. It is crucial for the survival of mankind and its future protection.

ROLE OF MICRO BUSINESSES

- Micro businesses play a vital role in the economy but often face challenges in achieving long-term sustainability.
- To overcome these challenges, they should adopt sustainable practices, such as energy efficiency, sustainable supply chains, and responsible waste management.

ROLE OF MICRO BUSINESSES

- Integrating social and environmental values into business operations and fostering a culture of sustainability can also positively impact the business.
- By implementing these practices, small businesses can reduce their environmental footprint, increase competitiveness, and ultimately increase profitability.

ROLE OF MICRO BUSINESSES

- Micro businesses may have less than ten employees, but comprise nearly 90% of the German economy.
- Clients and customers respond well to companies that choose to place value on the planet and people instead of pure profit.

ROLE OF MICRO BUSINESSES

- SMEs are a powerful presence in the global business landscape.
- They account for 90% of businesses worldwide, generate two-thirds of all jobs, sustain the livelihoods of over two billion individuals, and play a critical role in the seamless operation of global supply chains.

Small and Medium sized Enterprises

- Despite their significant influence, many SMEs have yet to fully address environmental, social, and governance (ESG) concerns.
- The reasons behind this are clear - small businesses are defined by the EU as having 11-49 employees and annual revenues below €10 million, while medium-sized businesses have 50-249 employees and revenues up to €50 million.
- Owners and managers of these enterprises are often overwhelmed with their responsibilities and have fewer resources compared to larger corporations, making it challenging for them to address issues like climate change or discrimination.

Small and Medium sized Enterprises

- They lack the time, expertise, resources, or funds needed to tackle these problems.
- However, it is crucial for SMEs to contribute to creating a better world - not only for their own benefit but for the greater good.
- Adopting sustainable business practices can improve the profits both in the environmental and traditional sense.

Profitability through sustainability

- Our goal is to highlight that sustainability is not just a moral choice; it is a strategic one.
- By meeting the demand for eco-conscious products, businesses can contribute to public health, improve the environment, and create a positive impact on society.
- Moreover, the cost savings involved in sustainable practices can offset the initial investment, proving that adopting sustainable business practices is not just about being environmentally responsible.

Profitability through sustainability

- Small businesses are increasingly leading the way in creating a sustainable future, with millennials driving the market.
- Companies that prioritise the planet and people over pure profit are gaining traction.
- Adopting sustainable practices can improve profits in both environmental and traditional senses, meet demand for eco-conscious products, improve public health and environment, and increase positive brand association.

Profitability through sustainability

- Cost savings can offset the costs of integrating sustainable initiatives, making investing in a sustainability plan for small businesses a wise investment for the future.
- Business leaders must rethink their business models and value chains to create intelligent, efficient, sustainable, and resilient products, operations, and services.
- By embedding digital and sustainability into their operations, 80% of a product's environmental impacts are linked to design decisions.

Profitability through sustainability

- Sustainable practices, such as circular design, reduce environmental footprints, improve cost and resource use efficiency, and make manufacturers more resilient to supply chain shortages.
- While many leaders are unclear on the business case for sustainability, tomorrow's economy must decouple growth from resource consumption.
- Companies must prioritise sustainability and make it a competitive advantage.

02

OBJECTIVES

OBJECTIVES

- Sustainability is a crucial concept aimed at creating a better future for our planet and its resources.
- For those new to the concept, it's essential to seek advice, review current realities, and set goals.
- From there, strategise and take immediate action.
- Even small businesses can make a significant impact on climate change, as even small changes can significantly reduce their impact.

OBJECTIVES

- The Sustainability Starter Kit is designed to serve as a comprehensive guide for micro organisations to build into their day-to-day operations as well as future sustainability initiatives.
- The manual addresses the importance of sustainability, compliance with EU regulations, attracting conscious consumers, reducing costs, and building a resilient business model.
- It is tailored for micro businesses looking to make a positive impact on the environment, society, and on their bottom line.

03

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Thank You
Any questions?

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